

NOTES

Studies in Some Ni(II) and Cu(II) Complexes

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Polyhydroxy aromatic ligand complexes of Ni(II) of the type $[ML_2]enH_2^{2+}$, where L = catechol or pyrogallol and Cu(II) complexes of the type $[M(L)(en)]$, where L = catechol, pyrogallol or 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene and en = ethylenediamine, have been reported earlier^{1,2}. The compounds have been prepared either by the addition of ligand (L) to aqueous solution of bisethylenediamine metal complexes or by the addition of ethylenediamine to mixture of M+L in 1 : 2 ratio. Similar studies have been carried out with tertiary bases in the present investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL AND DISCUSSION

The compounds were synthesised by using following two methods :

(i) To the aqueous solution of nickel chloride or copper sulphate and catechol, pyrogallol or 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene in 1 : 2 ratio was added pyridine, β - or γ -picoline till the pH was ~ 6.0 . The solids obtained were washed with water, impregnated with tertiary base. Excess tertiary base was washed out with ether. The solids were dried and analysed.

(ii) To the aqueous solution of $[Ni(A)_4]Cl_2$ or $[Cu(A)_4]SO_4$ (where A = pyridine, β - or γ -picoline), prepared by methods suggested earlier³, was added an excess of catechol, pyrogallol or 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene. The solids obtained were washed with water, impregnated with tertiary base. Excess tertiary base was washed out with ether. The solids were dried and analysed.

The compounds obtained by both the methods, in case of same set of metal ion, polyhydroxy ligand and tertiary base, were same. The copper(II) complexes obtained were brownish red in colour and Ni(II) complexes had light green colour. The analytical data are stated in Table 1.

In case of copper complexes of catechol and pyrogallol and in case of reactions with α -picoline, solids are obtained but they do not correspond to any definite composition.

The magnetic susceptibility of the complexes have been recorded in Table 1. Visible and I.R. spectra have also been obtained in the region 400–1000 $m\mu$ and 4000–400 cm^{-1} respectively.

Ni(II) complexes of catechol and 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene have composition $[ML_2](AH^+)_2$ where A = pyridine, β - or γ -picoline. In case of direct reaction the added tertiary base gets protonated and acts as a cation. In the case of the reverse reaction the

tertiary base is replaced from the complex by catechol or 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene. The liberated tertiary base gets protonated and acts as the cation.

In case of pyrogallol, however, a mixed ligand complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{pyro})(\text{A})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (where A = pyridine, β - or γ -picoline) was obtained. The reason why a compound of the above type is not obtained is not very clear. The compound is not soluble in any solvent, not even in DMF and DMSO and hence conductance measurements were not possible.

TABLE I

Compound	% calc.		% found		B.M.
	Ni	N	Ni	N	
1. $[\text{Ni}(\text{cat})_2]^{2-}(\text{pyH}^+)_2$	13.49	6.44	13.61	6.22	3.14
2. $[\text{Ni}(\text{cat})_2]^{2-}(\beta\text{-picH}^+)_2$	12.68	6.05	12.48	6.15	3.03
3. $[\text{Ni}(\text{cat})_2]^{2-}(\gamma\text{-picH}^+)_2$	12.68	6.05	12.61	5.85	3.08
4. $[\text{Ni}(2,3\text{-dinaph})_2]^{2-}(\text{pyH}^+)_2$	10.97	5.23	10.85	5.00	3.15
5. $[\text{Ni}(2,3\text{-dinaph})_2]^{2-}(\beta\text{-picH}^+)_2$	10.42	4.97	10.25	4.71	3.05
6. $[\text{Ni}(2,3\text{-dinaph})_2]^{2-}(\gamma\text{-picH}^+)_2$	10.42	4.97	10.28	4.75	3.11
7. $[\text{Ni}(\text{pyro})(\text{py})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	18.59	4.43	18.35	4.30	3.00
8. $[\text{Ni}(\text{pyro})(\beta\text{-pic})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	17.79	4.24	17.65	4.26	2.98
9. $[\text{Ni}(\text{pyro})(\gamma\text{-pic})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	17.79	4.24	17.68	4.12	2.93
	Cu	N	Cu	N	B.M.
10. $[\text{Cu}(2,3\text{-dinaph})(\text{py})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	18.86	4.16	18.74	3.90	1.85
11. $[\text{Cu}(2,3\text{-dinaph})(\beta\text{-pic})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	18.11	3.98	17.80	3.85	1.82
12. $[\text{Cu}(2,3\text{-dinaph})(\gamma\text{-pic})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	18.11	3.98	17.95	4.10	1.79

In case of Cu(II) complexes with 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene mixed ligand complex $[\text{Cu}(2,3\text{-dinaph})(\text{A})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (where A = pyridine, β - or γ -picoline) was obtained.

In case of catechol or pyrogallol though the metal percentage of the isolated solid agrees with the composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{A})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, the percentage of nitrogen was found to be less than expected. This may be because some of the tertiary base is replaced by water during washing. This could not be checked even on using more of the tertiary base as the washing ligand.

The number of water of crystallisation could not be determined by heating at 110° , because, in adducts, coordinated tertiary base is also known to be lost at lower temperature^{4,5}. Some compounds (adducts of complexes of Cu and Ni) on being heated at 110° for 6–8 hrs. showed complete absence of nitrogen. The residual weight corresponded to the loss of water of crystallisation and the coordinated pyridines. In other cases, however, loss of tertiary base was not complete and constant weight of the residue could not be obtained.

The visible absorption spectra of the Nickel complexes in aqueous solution exhibit two shoulders at ~ 410 and $\sim 510 \text{ m}\mu$, corresponding to square planer geometry. However, in the solid state the complex has magnetic moment of the order $\sim 2.9\text{--}3.1$ B.M. corresponding to two unpaired electrons. Square planar Ni(II) complexes are however, expected

to be diamagnetic. This shows some difference in structure in solid state⁶. However, more data is required to resolve this point.

Since the magnetic moments of the copper complexes are ~ 1.8 B.M., the presence of one unpaired electron is indicated. The possible structures are square planar or tetrahedral. Visible absorption spectra, however, exhibit one broad peak at ~ 640 m μ . This corresponds to combination of ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$; ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions⁷ and indicates D_{4h} symmetry of the complex.

The I.R. spectra exhibit the bands corresponding to the tertiary bases and the polyhydroxy ligand molecules. Spectra in the far I.R. region could not be available.

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